

Biotype 2 had the longest chromosomes and biotype 1 had the shortest. Biotype 2 had the widest X and Y chromosomes, while biotype 1 and 3 measurements were almost equal.

During *anaphase I* measurements of the chromosome clumps at the two poles of the cells showed the lengths and widths of chromosome groupings in biotype 2 differed significantly from those of biotype 1 but not from biotype 3.

At *telophase I* the groupings of chromosomes at two opposite poles of the cells were almost equal for all three biotypes.

Chromosomal aberrations, such as loose pairings of paired homologous bivalents as well as fragmentations of chromosomal deletions occurred more frequently among biotype 1 individuals, followed by biotype 3. □

Variations^a in nuclear and chromosome measurements of brown planthopper biotypes 1, 2, and 3 during prophase. IRRI, 1981-82.

Prophase I substages	Biotype 1	Biotype 2	Biotype 3
<i>Leptonema</i>			
Nuclei: <i>aml</i> and <i>amw</i>) ns	31.75μ and 26.50μ, highest	29.90μ and 24.00μ, lowest	30.50μ and 24.75μ intermediate
<i>Zygonema</i>			
Autosomes)	no difference	no difference	no difference
Sex chromosome)			
<i>Pachynema</i>			
Autosomes <i>rml</i>)	11.11 mm, lowest) ns	12.43 mm, intermediate	13.17 mm, highest
Sex chromosome <i>rml</i>)			
<i>Diplonema</i>			
Autosomes <i>aml</i> ^b	5.92μ, lowest	8.08μ, highest	7.08μ, intermediate
Sex chromosome <i>aml</i>	7.50μ	5.00μ	5.00μ
<i>Diakinesis</i>			
Chromosomes <i>aml</i> ^c	4.35μ, highest	3.77μ, intermediate	3.39μ, lowest

^a*aml* = absolute mean length, *amw* = absolute mean width, *rml* = relative mean length, ns = not significant at 5% level by analysis of variance and Duncan's multiple range test. ^bBiotype 1 significantly different from biotypes 2 and 3; biotypes 2 and 3 not significantly different from each other at 5% level by analysis of variance and Duncan's multiple range test. ^cBiotype 1 significantly different from biotype 3 but not from biotype 2; biotype 2 not significantly different from biotype 3 at 5% level by analysis of variance and Duncan's multiple range test.

Rice thrips control by foliar insecticides

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Rice thrips *Baliothrips biformis* (Bagnall) is a minor rice pest in the Punjab. It usually attacks the late transplanted crop. BHC 10% dust applied at 10 kg/ha (2.5 kg ai/ha) is the only recommended control.

Foliar insecticides for thrips control were field-tested at the Regional Research Station at Gurdaspur. Thirty-day-old PR103 seedlings were transplanted in 20-m² plots in a randomized block design with 3 replications. They were sprayed with 10 insecticides 15 days after transplanting. BHC was included as a check.

Thrips/5 hills were recorded before treatment and 3 and 7 days after treatment (DAT). Population reduction was calculated as:

$$\text{Percent reduction} = \frac{\text{Insects counted per sample unit after treatment} \times \text{Insects counted in the control before treatment}}{\text{Insects counted per sample unit before treatment} \times \text{Insects counted in the control after treatment}} \times 100$$

Demeton-o-methyl, quinalphos, fenitrothion, fenitrothion, monocrotophos, endosulfan, and phosphamidon controlled thrips better than BHC dust at 3 DAT

Efficacy of foliar insecticides for control of rice thrips, Gurdaspur, Punjab, India, 1982.

Treatment ^a	Population before treatment (no./5 hills)	Percent reduction after	
		3 days ^b	7 days ^c
BHC	110	88 b	99
Chlorpyrifos	63	77 c	99
Demeton-methyl	70	96 a	97
Endosulfan	93	92 ab	98
Fenthion	52	93 ab	99
Fenitrothion	79	93 ab	99
Methyl parathion	59	87 b	97
Monocrotophos	84	92 ab	98
Phosaione	60	80 c	100
Phosphamidon	64	90 ab	99
Quinalphos	57	93 ab	95
Untreated check	68	—	—

^aBHC was applied at 2.5 kg ai/ha; all other insecticides were used at 0.5 kg ai/ha. ^bFigures followed by the same letter in a column are not significantly different at 5% level. ^cAll treatments were significantly different from the untreated check but did not differ from each other.

(see table). Phosalone and chlorpyrifos were least effective. However, all insecticides reduced thrips population by more than 95%.

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